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Analysis of Coarse Aggregate Sources Effects on Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete

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Abstract

Substandard materials, specially, low-quality cement concrete as construction materials leading the failure of structure in Nepal before design life and some structure fails during the construction phase. To analysis Coarse Aggregate Sources Effects on Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete. Laboratory tests were conducted to find the properties of coarse aggregates from selected 4 river sources and compressive strength test was conducted using UTM machine for altogether 48 cubes.

After conducting the test for properties of specific gravity, loose bulk density, water absorption and aggregate abrasion properties value of coarse aggregate sources were found in the range of (2.56-2.79), (1568.38-1707.06) kg/m³, (1.76-1.94) %, (18.75-26.5) % respectively. The compressive strength value of all 48 samples were obtained greater than the minimum strength provided by M20 grade and ranges from 20.64 N/mm² to 32.47 N/mm². The value of mean compressive strength of sixteen combinations were obtained from test was differ from each other. Chisang coarse aggregates achieved more value of average compressive strength than other sources. Two-way ANOVA analysis shows that there is significance difference in mean compressive strength of concrete made from different coarse aggregates source. This study concluded that all coarse aggregates sources and concrete made from it can be used for residential building construction propose and other concrete work of M20 grade.

1. Introduction

The use of concrete in construction sector is very high and dominant construction material in developing countries like Nepal. The failure of concrete structure in such countries may lead huge loss of life and property.

Compressive strength of the concrete is the most significant property of concrete. The compressive strength is obtained by testing concrete specimen after curing 28 days in a universal compressive strength test machine. The uses of poor-quality ingredient in cement concrete production seriously affect the ultimate compressive strength of concrete. A coarse aggregate is the major constituent of the concrete and it takes part in the strength of concrete. It is the main source of strength in concrete. Nepal being small world with natural diversity, it needs a special attention before river bed material extraction based on properties and suitability.

2. Problem Statement

After detail effects study of cement brands effects on concrete strength (Mishra and Sharestha, 2018; Mishra et al., 2020), it is to study on coarse aggregates. The 15th national plan prepared by NPC set the target of '*Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepali*' (15th Plan, 2019). To achieve the goal of this presumption various infrastructure are construction and going to be constructed like airport, stadium, fast track, hydropower plant by using the huge amount of concrete as construction material. Nepal has altogether 6,000 rivers (including rivulets and tributaries)(*State of Water : Nepal*, n.d.). Coarse aggregate is main source of strength of concrete, but no such study is done in emerging cities like Urlabari municipality though National Building Code has assure to maintain minimum of M20 grade of concrete for residential building. So,the study of coarse aggregate properties and its effects on compressive strength is essential from technical as well as economical aspect.

3. Objectives

The study aims to analyse the effects of coarse aggregates from different sources on the compressive strength of concrete used in study area.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Properties of Coarse Aggregates

The aggregates retained in the 4.75 mm sieve are coarse aggregates and possess different physical, chemical, mechanical and thermal properties (Mehta, 1999). A study done by (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) calculate the different properties of different natural coarse aggregates sources are tabulated as

Table 4. 1: Properties of Coarse Aggregate Sources (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018)

Source	Loose bulk density	Specific Gravity	Water absorption (%)	Flakiness Index (%)	Elongation Index (%)	Aggregate Impact Value (%)	Aggregate Crushing value (%)	Aggregate Abrasion value (%)
KQ	1541	2.50	1.01	18.24	25.44	12.46	21.90	21.26
RQ	1622	2.88	0.69	16.03	27.87	10.09	20.30	18.68
EQ	1530	2.81	0.67	16.70	23.96	9.12	19.70	18.32

A research work done by (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019b) determine the following properties of coarse aggregates sources to study its effect on concrete of various grade.

Table 4. 2: Properties of Coarse aggregates sources (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019b)

Sources	Dry-rodded bulk density (kg/m ³)	Specific Gravity	Void Ratio	Porosity
Panauti	1500	2.45	0.63	0.39

Melamchi	1680	2.59	0.54	0.35
Chauki Dada	1592	2.64	0.66	0.40
Khopasi	1675	2.73	0.63	0.39
Kaaldhunga	1519	2.70	0.78	0.44

4.2 Compressive Strength of Concrete

The compressive strength of concrete depends on the water to cement ratio, degree of compaction, ratio of cement to aggregate, bond between mortar and aggregate, and grading, shape, strength and size of the aggregate (Abdullahi, 2012)

One of the most common methods to evaluate concrete performance is by measuring the compressive strength of hardened concrete (f_c') at an age of 28 days. This test can be done by breaking a concrete specimen in a compression testing machine. The specimens can be a standard cube specimen of $150 \times 150 \times 150$ mm³ or a standard cylindrical concrete specimen of 150 mm \times 300 mm. Strength of cylinder is roughly 80% of the strength of the cube (Tantawi, 2015).

4.3 Effect of Ingredients on Compressive Strength of Concrete

Research work done by (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) found in their study is that among twelve samples only five mixtures had above the minimum cube compressive strength of 25N/mm² and they recommended these samples for the construction of the reinforced load-bearing building structural members. Other three mixtures had above the compressive strength of 20N/mm² and recommended for the use in plain concrete construction while the remaining four mixtures had their compressive strength between 19.3N/mm² and 17.9N/mm². Finally, they concluded that the compressive strength depends on aggregate source.

A study by (Abdullahi, 2012) concluded in his study that the concrete made from river gravel has the highest workability followed by crushed quartzite and crushed granite aggregates. The compressive strength was noted highest value with concrete made from quartzite aggregate followed by river gravel and then granite aggregate. The compressive strength models were proposed as a function of age at curing and he advised to concrete practitioners to use the aggregate made from quartzite for concrete work.

According to (Hossain et al., 2015), test results among the 108 numbers of concrete cylinder (150 mm \times 300 mm) were tested using six nominal sizes (12.5, 19.0, 25.0, 32.0, 38.0 and 50.0 mm) of coarse aggregate and six cement contents (150, 200, 250, 300, 350 and 400 kg/m³ of concrete) considering water-cement ratio of 0.5 by weight reveal that the strength of concrete increases with the increase in cement content of concrete. The strength of concrete also increases with the increase in size of coarse aggregate for a cement content of 150 kg/m³. However, for concrete with cement content more than 150 kg/m³, strength increases with the increase in size of coarse aggregate up to 25 mm and decreases as the aggregate size increases beyond 25 mm.

In the study done by (Rao & Sen, 2017), it was seen that quarry dust concrete required more water to achieve adequate workability when compared to normal concrete. The compressive strength and split tensile strength of all grades of quarry dust concrete tends to reduce by a certain percentage when water cement ratio was increased from 0.5 to 0.65 in steps of 0.05.

5. Research Gap

Only few researches have been done in Nepal to ensure the effect of aggregate sources on compressive strength of concrete. In the research paper published by (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019a), researchers show the coarse aggregate source had significant variation in the compressive strength of various grade of nominal concrete mix. Among few researches done in this research area, the research done in this research topic cannot cover the emerging city like Urlabari Municipality and most of the researches are oriented in Kathmandu valley and other major cities of Nepal. To fulfil the gap in research between developed cities with developing cities this research will be carried in the rivers sources from where supplies are made in Urlabari Municipality area.

6. Methodology

6.1 Study area

This is an experimental study with the aim of identify the effect of coarse aggregates from different sources of eastern region of Nepal in compressive strength of concrete produce in that area. This research mainly focuses the concrete production in Urlabari Municipality.

6.2 Sam

The fine and coarse aggregates collected from these four sources were used to make concrete cube as per following combination shown in *Table 6.1* below. Three cubes were made from all sixteen combinations for M20 grade concrete. There were altogether 48 cubes for M20 grade of nominal mix concrete.

Table 6. 1: Research matrix (combination of fine and coarse aggregates)

Sample codes	CC	BC	MC	RC
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CF=Chisang fine quarry

BF=Bakrah fine quarry

MF= Mawa fine quarry

RF= Ratuwa fine quarry

CC= Chisang coarse quarry

CF	CFCC	CFBC	CFMC	CFRC
BF	BFCC	BFBC	BFMC	BFRC
MF	MFCC	MFBC	MFMC	MFRC
RF	RFCC	RFBC	RFMC	RFRC

6.3 Data Collection

For this research work fine and coarse aggregates from different sources were collected from the following locations.

Table 6. 2: Locations of aggregates collection from different sources

S.N.	Fine and Coarse aggregates sources	Northing	Easting	Reduced Level
1	Chishang Khola	26°42'44"	87°29'27"	213m
2	Bakraha Khola	26°43'13"	87°37'51"	146m
3	Mawa Khola	26°43'24"	87°40'01"	163m
4	Ratuwa Khola	26°44'09"	87°42'29"	182m

The following test was carried out on the labs of "Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal-MBMAN". During laboratory test of concrete properties of cement, water/cement ratio and use of chemical and admixtures were remained unchanged throughout the study.

6.3.1 Test on Coarse Aggregate Properties

1. Specific Gravity and Water Absorption Test

Specific gravity test of aggregates was conducted to measure the strength or quality of the material.

Water absorption test was conducted to determine the water holding capacity of coarse and fine aggregates. The following procedure were conducted to determine the specific gravity and water absorption of fine and coarse aggregates as per ("IS 2386-3 (1963)).

2. Loose Bulk Density Test

Loose bulk density is the ratio of loose mass per unit volume of aggregate samples which was calculated by using the procedure mention below as per(*IS 2386-3 (1963) Methods of Test for Aggregates f.Pdf*, n.d.) .

3. Los Angeles Abrasion Test

This test on aggregates is the measure of aggregate toughness and abrasion resistance such as crushing, degradation and disintegration. The test procedure of abrasion test on aggregates were involved following steps as per (“IS 2386-4 (1963)).The 10 kg aggregate sample was taken and placed on the Los Angeles apparatus and fixed the cover.

6.3.2 Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength of concrete was done as per guideline given by (*IS 516 (1959): Method of Tests for Strength of Concrete*, 1959). Three specimens of same aggregate combination were prepared as per IS 516 (1959) and was tested on universal compression testing machine after 28 days of curing and crushing strength of the specimen was recorded.

Compressive Strength of Concrete cube =

$$\frac{\text{Peak load at which it break (N)}}{\text{Corss – sectional area of that cube(mm}^2\text{)}}$$

Mean Compressive strength =

$$\frac{\text{Sum of compressive strength of three sample}}{3}$$

7. Analysis of Data

7.1 Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete

Compressive strength test of the various sample combination of aggregates from different sources, the mean obtained value of compressive strength of each combination was compared with standard compressive strength of concrete mix (M20 grade). The comparison between tested value and standard value analysed the effect of aggregate sources on compressive strength of concrete.

For the test of significance of test results two-way ANOVA test was carried out based on hypothesis testing. The dependent variable was the compressive strength with respect to independent variable (fine and coarse aggregates). Two-way ANOVA table was set of as Table 7.1.

Table 7.1: Setting up Two-way ANOVA table

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean sum of Square	F-ratio
Between rows	SSR	(r-1)	$MSR = \frac{SSR}{r-1}$	$F_r = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$
Between columns	SSC	(c-1)	$MSC = \frac{SSC}{c-1}$	$F_c = \frac{MSC}{MSE}$
Errors	SSE	(r-1)(c-1)	$MSE = \frac{SSE}{(r-1)(c-1)}$	
Total	SST	rc-1		

Where,

SSR=Sum of Square of Rows

SSC= Sum of Square of Columns

SSE= Squares due to Error

SST= Total of Sum of Squares
r= No. of Rows
c=No. of Columns

7.2 Process Capability Analysis

Process capability analysis was conducted to identify the overall test procedure of compressive strength of concrete cube from different samples meet the desire specifications of the test by adopting the following procedure(Evans & Lindsay, 2013):

- At first, the mean and standard deviation of observation data of compressive strength was calculated.
- Then, process capability ratio (Cp) was calculated using formula $Cp = \frac{USL - LSL}{6s}$, where,
USL= Upper Specification Limit
LSL= Lower Specification Limit
s = Standard Deviation of the process
- Interpretation of Cp was done as:
 - a) For $Cp=1$, then normal process is capable of creating product that meet the desired design specification
 - b) For $Cp<1$, then the normal process is not capable of creating product that meet the desired design specification.
 - c) For $Cp>1$, then the normal process is capable of creating product that meet the desired design specification
 - d) Larger the value of Cp, better the product quality.
- After that the process capability index was calculated using formula $Cpk = \text{Minimum value of } [\frac{USL - \mu}{3s}, \frac{\mu - LSL}{3s}]$, where
USL= Upper Specification Limit
LSL= Lower Specification Limit
 μ = Process mean
s = Standard Deviation of the process
- At last, Interpretation of Cpk was done as:
 - a) $Cpk<1$, it indicates that the process does not conform to specification
 - b) $Cpk>1$, it indicates that the process conforms to specification
 - c) $Cpk=0$, it indicates the average is equal to one of the specification limits.
 - d) $Cpk=1$, it indicates the defect standard.

8. Result and Discussion

8.1 Properties of Coarse aggregates

The physical and mechanical properties of different coarse aggregates sources selected in this study are shown in Table 8.1. These properties are obtained by the procedure comply with IS standard series of test on properties of aggregates

Table 8.1: Physical and mechanical properties of Course aggregates sources

S.N.	Sample Codes	Specific Gravity	Loose Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	Water Absorption (%)	Aggregate Abrasion value (%)
1	CC	2.73	1682.65	1.76	18.75
2	BC	2.57	1597.06	1.83	26.5
3	MC	2.79	1707.06	1.94	23.5
4	RC	2.56	1568.38	1.77	21.45

The test results showed the SG of CC, BC, MC and RC are 2.73, 2.57, 2.79 and 2.56. It is seen that the MC source has highest value of SG and RC source possess low value of SG among four. (Reddy et al., 2015) used coarse aggregate having SG 2.85 in their study. Similarly a study done by (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019b) in the five coarse aggregates sources near Kathamandu Valley of Nepal, researchers determined the value of SG in the range of 2.45 to 2.73. (Mehta, 1999) writes values of specific gravity is depending upon the aggregate's types. Some aggregates may have value of SG more than 3. Generally, aggregates having SG value of 2.5-3 are preferable for road construction (Lay, 2009).

From the experiment, the LBD of CC, BC, MC and RC were founded as 1682.65Kg/m³, 1597.06Kg/m³, 1707.06 Kg/m³and 1568.38Kg/m³respectively. The MC source have high value of LBD and RC source of coarse aggregate has low value of LBD among four sources taken into study. A study done by(Ajagbe &Tijani, 2018) in Naigeria, calculated the value of LBD for three different coarse aggregates sources as 1530Kg/m³ to 1622Kg/m³. Similarly, (Reddy et al., 2015) used coarse aggregate having LBD 1691Kg/m³ in their research. Accordingly, (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019b) determined the LBD of five coarse aggregates sources ranges from 1500Kg/m³ to 1680Kg/m³.

The calculated value of water absorption capacity of CC, BC, MC and RC were 1.76%, 1.83%, 1.94% and 1.77 % respectively. It can be said that the aggregates from MC source absorb more water than other sources and CC source has low capacity to absorb water. (Reddy et al., 2015) used coarse aggregates having WA capacity of 0.90% in their study. Similarly, (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) determined the value of WA capacity of three coarse aggregates sample were in range of 0.67% to 1.01%. (Neville & Brooks, 2010) writes the value of WA should not greater than 2% if exceed soundness test is required.

The test result gave the aggregate abrasion value for CC, BC, MC and RC were 18.75%, 26.5%, 23.5% and 21.45% respectively. It is seen that the BC source has higher abrasion value and CC govern the less abrasion value. The maximum permissible abrasion value for cement concrete pavement as wearing surface is 30% and cement concrete pavement other than wearing surface is 16% (*IS 383 (1970): Specification for Coarse and Fine Aggregates From Natural Sources For Concrete*, n.d.). Similarly, (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) determines the abrasion value for three natural source as 18.32% to 21.90%.

8.2 Effect on Compressive Strength of Concrete

The mean compressive strength of different sixteen sample mix were obtained by laboratory test are tabulated as below in Table 8.2. The concrete cube made up of M20 grade of

nominal mix concrete give the minimum value of compressive strength of 20 N/mm² after 28 days curing testing on compression test machine(Tantawi, 2015). In the table 8.2, the 28 days compressive strength of all combinations ranges from 20.64 N/mm² to 32.47 N/mm². This study shows the concrete made from all the combinations of coarse aggregate sources meet the minimum value of compressive strength which should be given by M20 grade of concrete.

Table 8.2: Mean value of compressive strength of sixteen combinations

Sample Codes	CC	BC	MC	RC	Average	W/C Ratio (Constant)	Mix Proportion (Constant)	Cement Brand/grade (Constant)	Total no. of Cubes
CF	32.47	26.83	27.58	23.87	27.69	0.5	1:1.5:3 Nominal Mix of M20 Grade	SHIVAM 43 grade	12
BF	27.88	24.25	25.57	21.29	24.75				12
MF	28.54	26.78	26.30	22.86	26.12				12
RF	28.34	20.64	24.34	21.16	23.62				12
Average	29.31	24.63	25.95	22.30	-	Total			48

In respect of concrete made from coarse aggregate sources with different fine aggregate sources, CC gave the highest value of average of compressive strength of 29.31 N/mm², BC gave 24.63 N/mm², MC gave 25.95 N/mm² while RC gave 22.30 N/mm² which was the lowest value of average compressive strength among four coarse aggregate sources.

Figure 8.1: Average of mean compressive strength from Coarse aggregates samples

The compressive strength of cement concrete depend upon the various factors at which production of concrete is made. They may be water cement ratios, properties of cement, properties of aggregates, other admixtures used in concrete (Abdullahi, 2012). (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018) determined the 28 days compressive strength of concrete cube of M15 grade made up of different combinations of four fine and three coarse aggregates from different sources in the range from 17.9 N/mm² to 29.43 N/mm². Also in this study, the mean compressive strength of different sixteen combinations of different coarse aggregates form different sources with different fine aggregate sample are different. The significant difference in mean compressive strength of coarse aggregates analysed through two-way ANOVA test.

8.3 Two-way ANOVA Analysis of Mean Compressive Strength

The results of test statistic of two-way ANOVA test are presented in the Table 8.3 below. The 5% significance level is taken to obtain the value of F from the statistical table.

Table 8.3: Two-way ANOVA table of test statistic

Source of Variation	Sums of Squares SS	Degrees of freedom DF	Mean Squares MS	F-ratio (Calculated)
Between rows (Fine Source)	37.0502	3	12.3501	8.7832
Between columns (Coarse Source)	102.9092	3	34.3031	24.3959
Error (residual)	12.6549	9	1.4061	
Total	152.6144	15		

From statistical table, tabulated value of F-ratio for between columns i.e., F (3,9) at 0.05 level of significance is equal to 3.8625. As the calculated F-ratio 24.3959 is greater than that of tabulated F-ratio 3.8625, the null hypothesis, H₀ which is already set on analysis of data section of methodology chapter for coarse aggregate sample sources is rejected and the alternative hypothesis, H₁ is accepted. Hence there is significant difference between columns. That means there is significant difference in all the means of compressive strength of concrete produced by coarse aggregate sources.

8.4 Analysis of Test Process of Compressive Strength

From the calculation the value of process capability ratio (C_p) equal to 1.235 was greater than one, which indicates that the normal process is capable of creating product that meet the desired design specification. It means the overall test procedure of compressive strength test withing the upper and lower specification limits. From the process mean, the process capability

value is fall within the ± 3 times standard deviation. But the value of process capability index (C_{pk}) was less than one nearly equal to 0.2, that means the process does not conform to specification because the value of compressive strength is greater than the upper specification limit. Although C_{pk} state process not conform specification due to the higher value of compressive strength greater than upper specification limit, the higher value of compressive strength of concrete is good to use in concrete works for stable structure having higher loads.

Figure 0.2: Typical Diagram of Process Capability Chart

9. Conclusion and Recommendation

9.1 Conclusion

- All four coarse aggregates source meet their properties to use for the residential building construction purpose.
- The abrasion value of Chisang source is less than other so it can be used for the production of concrete in such construction where less abrasion is required such as rigid pavements.
- All samples from different sources achieved the value of mean compressive strength so, that all sources can be used for normal concrete works of construction.
- Coarse aggregates from Chisang source can be used in construction projects where less safety factor is considered and risk factor is high. Similarly, Mawa source can also be used for construction works where high strength is required. Furthermore, Bakraha and Ratuwa aggregates source can be used in the construction works where high safety factor is considered and risk factor is low.
- The coarse aggregates sources affect the strength of concrete made from them i.e., compressive strength of concrete vary from coarse aggregates sources.

9.2 Recommendation

- All aggregates sources used in this study can recommended for use of the production normal concrete and for residential building construction purpose.
- Some source whose properties is good and gives high compressive strength can recommended to use for high strength concrete works

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